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Electronic Supplementary Material for:

**Genome-wide sequencing identifies a thermal tolerance related synonymous
mutation in the mussel *Mytilisepta virgata***

Short title: Synonymous mutations associated with heat tolerance

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21 **Supplementary information in**

22 **2. Materials and Methods:**

23 **(a) Microhabitat-scale temperature and mortality statistics survey of *M. virgata* in**
24 **the field**

25 The preparing process of biomimetic thermal loggers is referring to previous study [1]:
26 a data logger iButton (DS1922L, Maxim Integrated) was inserted into the shell of a
27 mussel (shell length, 4-5 cm), whose soft tissues had been removed. And then, the
28 Robomussel was completed after filling Flame Retardant Compound (Scotchcast 2130,
29 3M, MN, USA) into the shell to waterproof the electronics. Before deployment, all
30 Robomussels were calibrated using a digital thermometer (Fluke 54II, Fluke, WA,
31 USA). The Robomussels were deployed in the microhabitats which were between 1.80
32 and 2.50 m above the chart datum (CD, the level from which depths displayed on a
33 nautical chart are measured). The temperatures in each microhabitat were recorded at
34 an interval of 1 h and an accuracy of 0.5°C.

35 The investigating process of *M. virgata* mortality at shaded and sun-exposed
36 microhabitats in summer was as follows: a total of 18 quadrats (25 × 25 cm) were
37 deployed (3 quadrates × 2 types of microhabitats × 3 microhabitats), and the number of
38 *M. virgate* in each quadrate was counted. A mussel was regarded as alive if the shell
39 kept closed or closed immediately when it was touched, while it was regarded as dead
40 if the mussel was empty or had no response when it was touched.

41 **(c) Sequence analysis and phylogenetic tree construction of the *M. virgata* *USP15***
42 **gene**

43 **Cloning and Sequencing of *M. virgata* *USP15* gene**

44 Total RNA was extracted from the adductor muscle of one mussel using TRIzol reagent
45 following the manufacturer's protocol (Invitrogen, China). The RNA purity was
46 determined by measuring the A260/A280 ratio on a Nanodrop spectrophotometer, while
47 RNA integrity was visually assessed by using 1% (w/v) agarose gel electrophoresis.
48 The cDNA was synthesized from isolated RNA by using PrimeScript™ II 1st Strand
49 cDNA Synthesis Kit (TaKaRa, China), following the manufacturer's protocol, and used

50 for PCR-amplification with the primer pair (uch-CDS) based on the annotated *M.*
51 *virgata* *USP15* gene (*MvUSP15* gene) from the *M. virgata* genome (table S1). PCR
52 reactions using LA Taq enzyme (TaKaRa, China) were performed on the thermal cycler
53 (Biometra) with an initial denaturation step of 94°C for 3 min, followed by 39
54 amplification cycles consisting of denaturation at 94°C for 30 s, annealing at 51°C for
55 30 s, elongation at 72°C for 2 min and 30 s, and the reactions were terminated with an
56 elongation step of 72°C for 10 min, followed by cooling at 4°C. The amplified products
57 were first purified using an AxyPrep™ DNA Gel Extraction Kit (Corning, China),
58 followed by an independent ligation process into the pMD19-T Vector system (TaKaRa,
59 China), then the recombinant plasmids were transformed into *Escherichia coli* Stellar
60 Competent Cells (Clontech). The cells were cultured on LB plates containing ampicillin.
61 The positive transformants were sent to Sangon Biotech (<https://www.sangon.com/>) for
62 sanger sequencing.

63 **Sequence Analysis**

64 R RIdiogram package [2] was used for mapping genome-wide information including
65 gene density and the distribution of gene family encoding deubiquitinating enzymes on
66 the idiogram. Database homology searching was performed using the BLAST program
67 at the NCBI website (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>). The homologous
68 sequences were listed in table S2.

69 **(d) Expression patterns of *MvUSP15* gene**

70 **Genotyping for *M. virgata* individuals**

71 Total DNA was extracted from the foot muscle of the mussels in both the heat-treated
72 group and control group with the CTAB method following the protocol based on
73 *Littorina saxatilis* [3]. The DNA purity was determined by measuring the A260/A280
74 ratio with a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, China), and the DNA
75 integrity was visually assessed by 1% (w/v) agarose gel electrophoresis.

76 PCR-amplification reactions using the primer pair (GT-454) designed based on
77 *MvUSP15* (table S1), were conducted with the rTaq enzyme (TaKaRa, China) using a
78 thermal cycler (Bio-Rad, China) with an initial denaturation step of 94°C for 3 min,

79 followed by 35 amplification cycles consisting of denaturation at 94°C for 30 s,
80 annealing at 40°C for 30 s, and elongation at 72°C for 30 s. The reactions were
81 terminated with an elongation step of 72°C for 3 min, followed by cooling at 4°C. The
82 amplified 454-bp products containing the synonymous mutation locus were sent to
83 Sangon Biotech (<https://www.sangon.com/>) for sanger sequencing. A total of 179
84 mussels have been genotyped successfully. Sanger sequencing files were viewed in
85 SnapGene software (<https://www.snapgene.com/>) and the genotypes of those 179
86 mussels were recorded in table S3.

87 **mRNA Expression of *MvUSP15* by Quantitative Real-Time Reverse** 88 **Transcription PCR**

89 Total RNA was extracted from the adductor muscle of mussels in both the heated-
90 treated group and the control group using TRIzol reagent following the manufacturer's
91 protocol (Invitrogen, China), and cDNA was synthesized using PrimeScript RT reagent
92 Kit with gDNA Eraser (Takara, China). The quantitative real-time PCR (qRT-PCR)
93 analysis was conducted to quantify the *MvUSP15* transcript levels on a CFX96 Real-
94 Time PCR Detection System (Bio-Rad). Specific primers (Qpcr1) for *MvUSP15* were
95 designed based on the identified sequence. The elongation factor 1 α (EF-1 α), was
96 chosen as the reference gene for internal standardization [4] (table S1). The melt curve
97 analysis was then conducted with 0.5°C increments from 65 to 95°C for 5 s per
98 temperature step. The qRT-PCR procedure was performed using 2 \times SYBR Premix Ex
99 Taq (TaKaRa, China) following the protocol: 95°C for 30 s, followed by 40 cycles of
100 95°C for 5 s and 60°C for 30 s. The amplification efficiencies for EF1 α and *MvUSP15*
101 were 108.2% and 105.2%, respectively. Each sample was tested in triplicate, and the
102 relative expression level of *MvUSP15* was calculated using the 2- $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method [69].
103 The calculation of relative *MvUSP15* expression levels was conducted using Bio-Rad
104 CFX Manager software (<https://www.bio-rad.com/>).

105

Supporting Information

106

107 **Figure S1.** Photos for *M. virgata* individuals in sun-exposed and shaded
108 microhabitats.

109 **Figure S2.** The overlaid heatmap shows the gene density (shown in gradient color)
110 and the tack labels refer to genes belonging to certain subfamilies of Deubiquitinating
111 enzymes (DUBs) found across the *M. virgata* genome [5], which consist of Josephin
112 domain-containing (MJD) proteases shown in the blue box, Otubain domain ubiquitin-
113 binding proteins (OTU) shown in purple circles, ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolases (UCH)
114 shown in orange triangles and two genes belonging to DUBs but without exact
115 annotation to any subfamilies shown as DUBs in the green box. *MvUSP15* gene was
116 shown in the red triangle at chromosome twelve.

117 **Figure S3.** Nucleotide and deduced amino acid sequences of the *MvUSP15* cDNA.
118 The numbering of nucleotides and amino acids is shown on the right side.

119 **Figure S4.** Alignments of conserved domains in *USP15* protein from species
120 belonging to different taxa.

121 **Figure S5.** The profile of absolute deviations of *MvUSP15* expression levels in
122 the mussels from the heat-treated group and control group. Different colors represent
123 different genotypes. Each triangle and circle represent the absolute deviation of
124 *MvUSP15* expression levels of an individual sampled from the shaded microhabitats
125 and sun-exposed microhabitats, respectively.

126 **Table S1.** Primer pairs were used in this research. The pair EF-1 α was from a
127 previous study.

128 **Table S2.** Homology sequences for *MvUSP15* are used for phylogenetic tree
129 construction. The GenBank sequence version number and scientific name of the species
130 are listed.

131 **Table S3.** The genotypes of 179 mussels in the heat-treated group and control
132 group.

133 **Table S4.** Two-factor ANOVA to measure the effect of genotype (G- or A-type)
134 and the sampling month on ABT of *M. virgata*

135 **Table S5.** The results of multiple comparisons using TukeyHSD analysis on
136 ABT of four clusters.

137 **Table S6.** Protein domain architectures and features of *MvUSP15*

138 **Table S7.** The results of multiple comparisons using TukeyHSD analysis on
139 *MvUSP15* expression levels of five clusters.

140 **Figure S1.** Photos for *M. virgata* individuals in sun-exposed and shaded
141 microhabitats.

142

143 **Figure S2.** The overlaid heatmap shows the gene density (shown in gradient color)
 144 and the tack labels refer to genes belonging to certain subfamilies of Deubiquitinating
 145 enzymes (DUBs) found across the *M. virgata* genome [5], which consist of Josephin
 146 domain-containing (MJD) proteases shown in the blue box, Otubain domain ubiquitin-
 147 binding proteins (OTU) shown in purple circles, ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolases (UCH)
 148 shown in orange triangles and two genes belonging to DUBs but without exact
 149 annotation to any subfamilies shown as DUBs in the green box. *MvUSP15* gene was
 150 shown in the red triangle at chromosome twelve.

151

152 **Figure S3.** Nucleotide and deduced amino acid sequences of the *MvUSP15* cDNA.

153 The numbering of nucleotides and amino acids is shown on the right side.

154

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ATGGCTGAAGGTGGTGTCTCGGAATGCAATGCTCAAAATGCCATTGATATTGACACGGCGGCCCTTGAAAAGCAGAAAAATGAATTGAAAGATTGCTGAAGAAGCCATTAAGCGGGAC 120
MAEGGVSECN AQNAIDIDTAALEKQKNELKD L L K P L K R D 40
GACAAATGGTATCTGCTTGTAGCAAAATGGTTTAAACAATGGAAGAAATATGTTGGCTATGAAAGTTGGGACTCCTTCAATGTTGGACAATCTGAAGCAAATCCCGGTCCCATAGATAAT 240
DKWYLLDAK WFKQWKKYVGYESWDSFNVGQSEANPGPIDN 80
TCTCAATTGCTCGATGAGAATGGAATGGAAGGACACCTTATAGATGAGTTAGATTATCAACTGTTTCCAGAGGAGGCTTGAATAAAGATCATGCTCTGGTATGGGTTGATGGAAGGA 360
S Q L L D E N G K L K E H L I D E L D Y Q L F P E E A W N K I M S W Y G L M E G 120
CAGACCAAATAGAGAGAAAAGTGGTGGCAAGGATGTTGTTAAACACTGCAAAGTAGAAGTTATCTTCTGGAAAATAAAAATGTGTGAAAATTCTAATCTAGAGAAGATAATTAGC 480
Q T P I E R K V I E Q G M F V K H C K V E V Y L L E I K M C E N S N L E K I I S 160
AAACAGATGAGTAGAGCTGAAACTATTGAGGATTTGGAGAAGGAACTGAAAAACATTTGAGATAGCAGAAAGAAAAGGAAAGTGCATTGTGGTATAAATATATGAGTAACACATACGAA 600
K Q M S R A E T I E D L E K E L R K T F E I A E E K E V R L W Y K Y M S N T Y E 200
CATCTTAGTAAAAAAGATAGTACATTACAAGATGCTGCATTGATTCTGGACAGGTAATTGTAATAGAACAGAAAAATGATGATGGGACATGGCCTAGACAAGCTAAAAGTACAAACAGT 720
H L S K K D S T L Q D A A L Y S G Q V I V I E Q K N D D G T W P R Q A K S T N S 240
TACAACAGTAGTTTACACTTCTACAAGTCCAGTTCAAGTGGATGATGATCCGGGTATGGGTCGCTATGGTTACTATGATACGACCAGGGAAGGGGTGGCAGTGTGGCACCTGGA 840
Y N S S S Y T S T R S S S S G Y D S G Y G S S Y G Y Y Q Y D Q R G G S V A P G 280
CTATGGTCTGTCAAATTTAGGAAACACTGTTTTTGAATTCAGCAATCAGTGTATGAGTAATGTGCCAAAGTTAACAGAATTTACTGAGTGAAAGTGGATTAATGAAGTGAAT 960
L C G L S N L G N T C F M N S A I Q C M S N V P K L T E Y L L S E R W I N E V N 320
GAGACCAATCCACTTGAATGGGTGGCGAAATAGCAAGGTCATATGCTGAGCTGAGCTCAAGGTCATGGTGTCTGGAAAATACAGTCATACTGTTCCTCGAAATTTTAAAGTGGCTGTAGGA 1080
E S N P L G M G G E I A R S Y A E L I K V M W S G K Y S H T V P R N F K V A V G 360
AGGTTTGGTCCACAGTTTTCTGGGTACCAGCAACAGGACTCCAGGAATTAATGGCTTTCTTATAGATGGCTTACATGAAGATCTGAACAGAATTCATAAAAAACCTTACATAGAACAG 1200
R F A P Q F S G Y Q Q Q D S Q E L L A F L L D G L H E D L N R I H K K P Y I E Q 400
AAAGATGCTGATGATCGATTAGTGAACCTGTGACCAAGGAATCCTGGGCAACTATAGAAAAAGGAATGATTCGTGATAGTTGACACTTTCCATGGACTACTCAAATCCACGGTACAT 1320
K D A D D R L D E L V A K E S W D N Y R K R N D S V I V D T F H G L L K S T V H 440
TGCCGGAATGTGATAAAATACAGTACTTTTGTATCTTTCTTACCTCCCTGTGAAGAAGGAACACAGATTGGAATAATCTGGGTTCCTACTAGTCTGAGAAA 1440
C P E C D K I S V T F D P F C Y L S L P L P V K K E R Q L E I F W V P L S P E K 480
AAACCTGTACAGTCAAATTAATAGTCCAAAGATGGGAAGTGTCTCAGATATGTGAAAATATTGTCAGAAAAAGTAGGAGTAGAACCCATAAAGATGGTAGTTACAGATGTTTACAAC 1560
K P V Q F K L I V P K M G S V S D M C K I L S E K V G V E P I K M V V T D V Y N 520
CATAGGTTCCATAAAGTGTTCAGTCCAGAAAGAAAGCCTTAGTTATATTTAGATAGGGATGATATTTTGTATATGAGGTACCTGTGTCCAAATCAGATGATCTGAAACTGTTTGTGTG 1680
H R F H K V F S P E E S L S Y I L D R D D I F V Y E V P V S K S D D P E T V V V 560
CCAATTTATAGAGAGAAAAGAACCAAGAAACAGTTACCATAGTGGTTTATCAACTTTTTGGTCAAGCTCTGCTGTCCAGTGTCCAGAAAAAATTGTACATATGAATCTTTGTAT 1800
P I Y M R E K K P R N S Y H S G S Y Q L F G Q P L L L P V S R K N C T Y E S L Y 600
AACACATTACTCCACAGAATATCACGTTATGTGAAAATGCCTTCAGAAGATGACAAATGGTGGATGGTAGAGAAAGATGGAATAAATGGTGAATGATAACAGTGTGGTGAAGAACTCA 1920
N T L L H R I S R Y V K M P S E D D K W M V E K D G K M V N D N S D G E K D S 640
GAAGATGAAGATAAAAATGATGAAGAAATGGACACCTCCAGTGATACAAAGGAAATTCATCAGAATGGAGATATTAATGGAGAACTTAATGGCCATGACAAAAAGCTAAACCTTACCT 2040
E D E D K N D E E M D T S S D T K E I H Q N G D I N G E L N G H D K K A K P S P 680
TTAATGTCAAATTTACTGTGGTGAATTCATACGGCAGTACAGAAATAAATACTCAAATTTGGATCGAGATGGGGAACCACTCAGATTAATAGTAGGACATATGATAGTGTGGACTGGAAT 2160
L M F K F T V V N S Y G S T E I N Y K L D R D G E P L R L N S R T Y V A V D W N 720
CCATTAGTCCAGGAAAAATTTATGATGACAAGGCTGTGAAGATTTTGAACAAGATGAGAGTATGAACTATAGAGCCAGAAGAAAACAAATATACAGCTTGGTATTGTCTGGATTTA 2280
P L A Q E K F Y D D K A A E D F E Q D E S M N Y R A Q K K Q I I Q L G D C L D L 760
TTTACAAAAGAAGAACAGCTAGGAGAAAATGACTTGTGGTATTGTCCAAGATGTAACAAAACATCAACAAGCTACCAAAAAGTTTACTTATGGTCACTGCGACAGCTTTTATTATTAC 2400
F T K E E Q L G E N D L W Y C P R C K K H Q Q A T K K F D L W S L P D V L I I H 800
CTTAAGAGATTCTCACAACAGATCTCAGAGACAAAATAGATGTGATAGTAGAATCCCTCCAAGAGGATGAGTATGAACAAATATGTTATCAATGCCAACCATGGACCTGCTAAT 2520
L K R F S Y N R Y F R D K I D V I V E F P P R G L S M N K Y V I N A N H G P A N 840
TATGACTTGATAGCCGCTCCTCAACATTATGGAGTCTCGGTGGAGGACATTACACGGCTTATGGCAAGAACAAAGAGAATAGTAATGGTACTACTTTGATGATTCTAGTGAAGTCC 2640
Y D L I A V S N H Y G G L G G H Y T A Y G K N K E N S E W Y Y F D D S S V S P 880
TCGTACAGAGGATGATGCTGTCAAGGAGCAGCTATGACTTGTATTAACAAAACGGACTCAGTGCCAAAGCAATTTCTAAGTCAGCCAGTAGGACGATGAATGGACAGTGTGACGAGGAC 2760
S S E D D V V S K A A Y V L V Y Q K R T Q C Q A N S K S A S R T M N G Q C D E D 920
ATGGAACATAA 2880
M E T * 923
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155 **Figure S4.** Alignments of conserved domains in *USP15* protein from species
 156 belonging to different taxa.

157

158 **Figure S5.** The profile of absolute deviations of *MvUSP15* expression levels in
159 the mussels from the heat-treated group and control group. Different colors represent
160 different genotypes. Each triangle and circle represent the absolute deviation of
161 *MvUSP15* expression levels of an individual sampled from the shaded microhabitats
162 and sun-exposed microhabitats, respectively.

163

164 **Table S1.** Primer pairs were used in this research.

Primer pair name	Forward primer (5' -> 3')	Reverse primer (5' -> 3')
uch-CDS	ATGGCTGAAGGTGGTGTCTC	TTATGTTTCCATGTCCTCGTCA
GT-454	TAAGGTCTGTTGTCTCATCCA	TATTACTAAATCTTCCTCACTCAT
Qpcr1	CCAGACGTTTTGATTATTCA	ACTATTCTCTTTGTTCTTGCC
EF-1 α	CTCTTCGTCTCCCACTCCAG	ACCAGGGAGAGCTTCAGTCA

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166

167 **Table S2.** Homology sequences for *MvUSP15* are used for phylogenetic tree construction. The
 168 GenBank sequence version number and scientific name of the species are listed.

Accession	Scientific name
XP_027312292.1	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>
XP_027312283.1	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>
XP_035283172.1	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>
XP_035283171.1	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>
XP_007893451.1	<i>Callorhinchus milii</i>
XP_007893449.1	<i>Callorhinchus milii</i>
CAG5118306.1	<i>Candidula unifasciata</i>
ELT95606.1	<i>Capitella teleta</i>
XP_042671665.1	<i>Centrocercus urophasianus</i>
XP_015275075.1	<i>Gekko japonicus</i>
XP_015274998.1	<i>Gekko japonicus</i>
AAI25124.1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>
NP_001239007.1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>
EAW97104.1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>
XP_015208775.1	<i>Lepisosteus oculatus</i>
XP_006633881.1	<i>Lepisosteus oculatus</i>
XP_013784175.1	<i>Limulus polyphemus</i>
XP_022252352.1	<i>Limulus polyphemus</i>
XP_013412555.1	<i>Lingula anatina</i>
XP_013412554.1	<i>Lingula anatina</i>
XP_003405221.1	<i>Loxodonta africana</i>
XP_010596742.1	<i>Loxodonta africana</i>
NP_001253886.1	<i>Macaca mulatta</i>
XP_036374081.1	<i>Megalops cyprinoides</i>
XP_036374079.1	<i>Megalops cyprinoides</i>
XP_005357999.1	<i>Microtus ochrogaster</i>
XP_005357998.1	<i>Microtus ochrogaster</i>
XP_021342964.1	<i>Mizuhopecten yessoensis</i>
XP_001363326.1	<i>Monodelphis domestica</i>
XP_001363243.1	<i>Monodelphis domestica</i>
AAH50042.1	<i>Mus musculus</i>
NP_001288557.1	<i>Mus musculus</i>
NP_081880.2	<i>Mus musculus</i>
CAG2211487.1	<i>Mytilus edulis</i>
XP_018417101.1	<i>Nanorana parkeri</i>
XP_018417099.1	<i>Nanorana parkeri</i>
GFO44983.1	<i>Plakobranthus ocellatus</i>
XP_025106449.1	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>
XP_025106450.1	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>
XP_020370655.1	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>
XP_020370654.1	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>
XP_006823492.1	<i>Saccoglossus kowalevskii</i>
KFM74598.1	<i>Stegodyphus mimosarum</i>
XP_038616391.1	<i>Tachyglossus aculeatus</i>

XP_038616374.1	<i>Tachyglossus aculeatus</i>
XP_010213622.1	<i>Tinamus guttatus</i>
XP_034626179.1	<i>Trachemys scripta elegans</i>
XP_034626172.1	<i>Trachemys scripta elegans</i>
XP_044278818.1	<i>Varanus komodoensis</i>
XP_044278817.1	<i>Varanus komodoensis</i>
XP_018111411.1	<i>Xenopus laevis</i>
XP_018111409.1	<i>Xenopus laevis</i>
XP_022104012.1	<i>Acanthaster planci</i>
XP_041533472.1	<i>Microtus oregoni</i>
XP_041533465.1	<i>Microtus oregoni</i>

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171 **Table S3.** The genotypes of 179 mussels in the heat-treated group and control group.

Sample ID	Genotyping results	Genotype	Microhabitat	Experimental Group	Experimental Temperature (°C)	Weight (g)	Heat-treated experiments data
1	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.97	2021/10/3
2	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.03	2021/10/3
3	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.37	2021/10/3
4	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.91	2021/10/3
5	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.4	2021/10/3
6	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	11.27	2021/10/3
7	AA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.37	2021/10/3
8	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	10.7	2021/10/3
9	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.96	2021/10/3
10	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.58	2021/10/3
11	GG	G-type	shaded	control	22	4.17	2021/10/3
12	AA	A-type	shaded	control	22	9.56	2021/10/3
13	GG	G-type	shaded	control	22	8.96	2021/10/3
14	GG	G-type	shaded	control	22	4.63	2021/10/3
15	GA	A-type	shaded	control	22	9.17	2021/10/3
16	GA	A-type	shaded	control	22	3.37	2021/10/3
17	AA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	5.4	2021/10/5
18	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	5.24	2021/10/5
19	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.22	2021/10/5
20	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.34	2021/10/5
21	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	5.63	2021/10/5
22	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.87	2021/10/5
23	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.3	2021/10/5
24	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.18	2021/10/5
25	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.83	2021/10/5
26	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	7.05	2021/10/5
27	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	7.05	2021/10/5
28	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	8.02	2021/10/5
29	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	6.43	2021/10/5
30	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	3.62	2021/10/5
31	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	6.23	2021/10/5
32	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	4.11	2021/10/5
33	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.25	2021/10/11
34	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.63	2021/10/11
35	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.68	2021/10/11
36	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.13	2021/10/11
37	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.68	2021/10/11
38	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	6.29	2021/10/11
39	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.32	2021/10/11
40	AA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	9.14	2021/10/11
41	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	10.79	2021/10/11
42	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	7.69	2021/10/11
43	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	10.01	2021/10/11

44	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	7.57	2021/10/11
45	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	9.66	2021/10/11
46	AA	A-type	shaded	control	22	12.65	2021/10/11
47	GA	A-type	shaded	control	22	6.53	2021/10/11
48	AA	A-type	shaded	control	22	10.89	2021/10/11
49	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	5.85	2021/10/12
50	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	6.71	2021/10/12
51	AA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.97	2021/10/12
52	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	6.11	2021/10/12
53	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.64	2021/10/12
54	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	6.12	2021/10/12
55	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	5.61	2021/10/12
56	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.13	2021/10/12
57	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	6.64	2021/10/12
58	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.68	2021/10/12
59	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	5.82	2021/10/12
60	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.84	2021/10/12
61	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	7.36	2021/10/12
62	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	5.7	2021/10/12
63	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	6.35	2021/10/12
64	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	5.95	2021/10/12
65	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	*	36	5.59	2021/10/18
66	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	*	36	4.97	2021/10/18
67	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	*	36	3.23	2021/10/18
68	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	*	36	5.51	2021/10/18
69	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	*	36	3.94	2021/10/18
70	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	*	36	4.43	2021/10/18
71	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	*	36	3.48	2021/10/18
72	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	*	36	3.93	2021/10/18
73	GG	G-type	shaded	*	36	4.57	2021/10/18
74	GG	G-type	shaded	*	36	4	2021/10/18
75	GG	G-type	shaded	*	36	3.89	2021/10/18
76	GG	G-type	shaded	*	36	6.65	2021/10/18
78	GG	G-type	shaded	*	36	6.51	2021/10/18
79	GG	G-type	shaded	*	36	5.65	2021/10/18
80	GA	A-type	shaded	*	36	4.12	2021/10/18
81	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.43	2021/10/19
82	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.24	2021/10/19
83	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.77	2021/10/19
84	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.21	2021/10/19
85	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	6.29	2021/10/19
86	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	6.42	2021/10/19
87	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.03	2021/10/19
88	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.46	2021/10/19
89	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	6.34	2021/10/19
90	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.87	2021/10/19
91	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.26	2021/10/19
92	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.69	2021/10/19
93	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.03	2021/10/19
94	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.19	2021/10/19

95	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.84	2021/10/19
96	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.76	2021/10/19
97	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.6	2021/10/19
98	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	7.27	2021/10/19
99	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.97	2021/10/19
100	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.85	2021/10/19
101	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	4.85	2021/10/19
102	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	5.3	2021/10/19
103	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	8.97	2021/10/19
104	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.95	2021/10/19
105	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3	2021/10/25
106	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.69	2021/10/25
107	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.77	2021/10/25
108	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.13	2021/10/25
109	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.23	2021/10/25
110	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.71	2021/10/25
111	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.13	2021/10/25
112	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.96	2021/10/25
113	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.47	2021/10/25
114	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.23	2021/10/25
115	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.63	2021/10/25
116	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.29	2021/10/25
117	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.32	2021/10/25
118	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	5.04	2021/10/25
119	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.37	2021/10/25
120	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.01	2021/10/25
121	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.45	2021/10/25
122	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.39	2021/10/25
123	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.94	2021/10/25
124	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.24	2021/10/25
125	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.84	2021/10/25
126	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	9.25	2021/10/25
127	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	9.42	2021/10/25
128	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	5.98	2021/10/25
130	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.84	2021/11/1
131	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	4.05	2021/11/1
132	AA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.45	2021/11/1
133	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.56	2021/11/1
134	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.43	2021/11/1
135	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.94	2021/11/1
136	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.25	2021/11/1
137	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.12	2021/11/1
138	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.8	2021/11/1
139	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.67	2021/11/1
140	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.75	2021/11/1
141	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	2.71	2021/11/1
142	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.58	2021/11/1
143	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	2.95	2021/11/1
144	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	2.7	2021/11/1
145	AA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.15	2021/11/1

146	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	3.22	2021/11/1
147	AA	A-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	2.81	2021/11/1
148	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	heat-treated	42	2.6	2021/11/1
150	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	3.27	2021/11/1
151	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.22	2021/11/1
152	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.65	2021/11/1
153	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.64	2021/11/1
154	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.64	2021/11/1
155	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.79	2021/11/1
156	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.63	2021/11/1
157	GA	A-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.9	2021/11/1
158	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	3.02	2021/11/1
159	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.79	2021/11/1
160	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.32	2021/11/1
161	GG	G-type	Sun-exposed	control	22	2.3	2021/11/1
162	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.58	2021/11/2
163	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	2.84	2021/11/2
164	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.86	2021/11/2
165	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.57	2021/11/2
166	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.27	2021/11/2
167	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.96	2021/11/2
168	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.14	2021/11/2
169	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.53	2021/11/2
170	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.05	2021/11/2
171	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.73	2021/11/2
172	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.9	2021/11/2
173	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.54	2021/11/2
174	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	2.45	2021/11/2
175	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	2.61	2021/11/2
176	GG	G-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.9	2021/11/2
177	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	2.59	2021/11/2
178	GA	A-type	shaded	heat-treated	42	3.56	2021/11/2
179	AA	A-type	shaded	control	22	2.55	2021/11/2
180	GG	G-type	shaded	control	22	3.41	2021/11/2
182	GG	G-type	shaded	control	22	2.98	2021/11/2
187	GG	G-type	shaded	control	22	2.02	2021/11/2

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174 **Table S4.** Two-factor ANOVA to measure the effect of genotype (G- or A-type) and the sampling
175 month on ABT of *M. virgata*

Source of variation	SS	DF	F	<i>p</i>
Month	31.73	2	32.95	< 0.001
Genotype	37.70	1	78.28	< 0.001
Month × Genotype	1.16	2	1.20	0.311
Residuals	20.23	42		

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178 **Table S5.** The results of multiple comparisons using TukeyHSD analysis on ABT of four clusters.

Two clusters for comparison	Difference in means	<i>p</i> value after adjustment
2-1	-2.71	< 0.001**
3-1	-0.46	0.47
4-1	-2.51	< 0.001**
3-2	2.44	< 0.001**
4-2	0.19	0.92
4-3	-2.05	< 0.001**

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181 **Table S6.** Protein domain architectures and features of *MvUSP15*

Name	Start residue	End residue	E-value
DUSP	36	132	$9.25e^{-34}$
Pfam: Ubiquitin_3	146	233	$7.2e^{-28}$
Pfam: UCH	282	896	$4.1e^{-78}$

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184 **Table S7.** The results of multiple comparisons using TukeyHSD analysis on *MvUSP15* expression
185 levels of five clusters.

Two clusters for comparison	Difference in means	<i>p</i> value after adjustment
2-1	-5.05	0.98
3-1	-16.29	0.50
4-1	83.53	< 0.001**
5-1	-7.44	0.96
3-2	-11.24	0.68
4-2	88.58	< 0.001**
5-2	-2.40	0.99
4-3	99.82	< 0.001**
5-3	8.84	0.89
5-4	-90.98	< 0.001**

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